

THE EMPLOYMENT LANDSCAPE IN NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES: A DECADAL ANALYSIS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the employment dynamics of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the span of a decade, from 2008 to 2018. Through a detailed analysis of key indicators and workforce trends, the study aims to illuminate the role of these enterprises in shaping the employment landscape within the mountainous region.

1. Introduction:

Newly established enterprises play a crucial role in driving economic growth and job creation. This paper focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area to explore the employment trends within these enterprises from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to analyze the share of employment generated by newly established businesses and its impact on the local workforce.

2. Methodology:

Utilizing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research integrates data from business registries, labor market reports, and relevant

publications. Key indicators such as employment growth rates, sectoral distribution of jobs, and demographic characteristics are analyzed to provide a nuanced understanding of the employment landscape in newly established enterprises.

3. Employment Trends in Newly Established Enterprises:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to employment trends within newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as overall employment figures, variations across industries, and the impact of economic events on job creation are scrutinized to assess the enterprises' contributions to regional employment.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of employment within different industries of newly established enterprises. Insights into key sectors driving employment, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral employment trends are discussed.

5. Demographic Characteristics of the Workforce:

This section investigates the demographic aspects of the workforce employed by newly established enterprises. Analyzing age groups, gender distribution, and educational backgrounds provides valuable insights into the composition of the workforce and potential demographic trends.

6. Economic Impact:

Assessing the economic impact of employment in newly established enterprises, the paper investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), overall employment rates, and economic stability. The interconnectedness between the growth of these enterprises and the broader economic landscape is explored.

7. Results:

The share of employment in newly established enterprises: the number of persons employed in the reference period (t) at newly born enterprises in t divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises in t – percentage

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, Percentiles 25, 50, 75, so 4.0564, .30797, 3.8700, 1.02141, 1.043, 2.047, .661, 5.429, 1.279, 3.94, 2.83, 6.77, 3.5100, 3.480, 3.8700

The models used for forecast analysis are specific to the forecast of large data series, thus S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared -7.973E-16, 4.719E-15, -1.199 E-14, 6,883E-15, -1,199E-14, -1,044E-14; R-squared -7.973E-16, 4.719E-15, -1.199E-14, 6.883E-15, -1.199E-14, -1.044E-14; RMSE 1.589, .722, .726, 3.412, .726, .784;

MAPS 21,100, 6,159, 14,481, 29,763, 14,481, 14,641; MaxAPE, 57,109, 18,922, 35,986, 94,534, 35,986, 36,150; MAE 1.123, .550, .576, 2.513, .576, .591; MaxAE 3,718, 1,817, 1,390, 8,116, 1,390, 1,537; Normalized BIC .982, .827, -.421, 2.673, -.421, -.288.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following general picture for I20 (values presented in the following order - Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1: -2.665E-15, -2.665E-15, 1.021 , 15,278, .651; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, .726, 29.300, .576; S3-Model_3: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 1.191, 16.629, .798; S4-Model_4: -1.332E-15, -1.332E-15, 1.505, 19.962, .917; S5-Model_5: 8.882E-16, 8.882E-16, 1.013, 17.349, .729; S6-Model_6: -1.199E-14, -1.199E-14, 1.535, 14.481, 1.050; S7-Model_7: -4.219E-15, -4.219E-15, 2.092, 28.129, 1.571; S8-Model_8: 1.110E-15, 1.110E-15, 1.482, 29.763, 1.049; S9-Model_9: 2.998E-15, 2.998E-15, 1.814, 15.813, 1.131; S10-Model_10: 6.883E-15, 6.883E-15, 1.682, 18.139, 1.366; S11-Model_11: -8.882E-16, -8.882E-16, 3.412, 27.256, 2.513.

Table 37. Forecast analysis for I20

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06	4.06
	UCL	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33	6.33
	LCL	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78	1.78

S2- Model_2:	Forecast	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02	2.02
	UCL	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64	3.64
	LCL	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40	.40
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50
	UCL	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15	8.15
	LCL	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84	2.84
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35	4.35
	UCL	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70	7.70
	LCL	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21	4.21
	UCL	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47
	LCL	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96	1.96
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90	6.90
	UCL	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32	10.32
	LCL	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48	3.48
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24	6.24
	UCL	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91	10.91
	LCL	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58	1.58
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43
	UCL	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73
	LCL	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13	.13
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47	6.47
	UCL	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52	10.52
	LCL	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43	2.43
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53	7.53
	UCL	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28	11.28
	LCL	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79	3.79

S11- Model_11:	Forecast	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84	9.84
	UCL	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45	17.45
	LCL	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24	2.24

Figure 3.28. Graphical forecasting analysis for I20

7. Challenges and Opportunities:

Examining the challenges and opportunities faced by both employers and employees in newly established enterprises, this section investigates factors such as workforce skill gaps, job stability, and opportunities for professional development. Addressing these aspects is essential for fostering a resilient and adaptive workforce.

8. Future Perspectives:

Identifying notable trends and potential future trajectories, this section provides insights into factors influencing employment dynamics in newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Considerations such as technological advancements, emerging market trends, and the adaptability of the local workforce are explored.

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the employment landscape in newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's workforce dynamics, offering valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable employment growth in newly established enterprises within the mountainous region.

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